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Operationalizing Explainable AI in the EU Regulatory Ecosystem

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Abstract—The European Union’s regulatory ecosystem presents challenges balancing legal and sociotechnical drivers for explainable AI systems. Core tensions emerge on dimensions of oversight, user needs and litigation. This paper maps provisions on algorithmic transparency and explainability across major EU data, AI, and platform policies using qualitative analysis. We characterize involved stakeholders and organizational implementation targets. Constraints become visible between useful transparency for accountability versus confidentiality protections. Through an AI hiring system example, we explore complications operationalizing explainability. Customization is required satisfying explainability desires within confidentiality and proportionality bounds. Findings advise technologists on prudent eXplainable AI technique selection given multi-dimensional tensions. Outcomes recommend policymakers balance worthy transparency goals with cohesive legislation enabling equitable dispute resolution.

■ **KEYWORDS** K.4.1.c Ethics, K.4.1.g Regulation, Explainable AI, Trustworthy AI

1. Introduction

The member states of the European Union (EU) aim to advance civil rights and national interests in developing and deploying information and communication technologies (ICT). The regulatory ecosystem set in place by the European Commission (EC) includes interconnected

policies related to foundational drivers like data economy and key enablers such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) and platform services, as evidenced by definitive planning documents like the EU Rolling Plan 2022¹ and 2030 Digital Compass². Attention towards dignity, freedom, and justice of

¹<https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/rolling-plan-ict-standardisation/rolling-plan-2022>

²<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX3A52021DC0118>

EU citizens³ is increasingly being translated into explainability - the ability to understand digital systems, especially those with sophisticated AI architectures.

Conventionally, eXplainable AI (XAI) techniques enhance the transparency of systems by focusing on making specific AI outputs comprehensible [1]. Yet, being able to deliver explanations regarding this understanding to several users, with different intentions and expertise, is an open-ended challenge. This is particularly relevant to convey enhanced transparency of sophisticated AI systems, encompassing their decision-making process, input data, and other internal variables as well as their design rationale.

In practice, it is often hard to determine what kind of information is required. An explanation could be reproved as not useful, or even jeopardize third party's privacy and Intellectual Property (IP). Thus, XAI applications shall favor AI innovation through major comprehension under the EU rule of law.

To the best of our knowledge, academic literature lacks a perspective examining AI explainability requirements across multiple EU regulations on data, AI, and platforms. This paper maps explainability requirements from EU regulations to operationalization dimensions and involved stakeholders. By the former, we intend the various functional targets related to implementing explainability in real-world systems [2]. The latter refers to entities like developers, users, and auditors across the AI system lifecycle [3], [1].

As a key remark, we note the lack of a single denotation of explainability for AI systems – intended as a proxy to either ensure regulatory oversight, serve AI systems' end users, and also a burden of proof under legal dispute – within the EU ecosystem. This ambiguity should not be interpreted as a lack of consensus or legislative expertise on AI systems. Instead, it reflects the need to balance EU citizen rights, business secrecy, and innovation across diverse contexts from system compliance to user services and litigation. Yet, we observe how the EU regulatory approach may limit end-users' legal recourse through AI system explanations.

³Encoded in the Charter of fundamental rights (EU 2012/c 326/02) <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:C2012/326/02>

The manuscript is organized as follows. Section 2 provides a background on operationalization of XAI techniques and legal considerations. Section 3 provides a policy content analysis of EU regulations on algorithmic explainability for data, AI, and platforms. Section 4 maps explainability desiderata in regulations informed by previous work defining dimensions and stakeholders. Section 5 highlights contexts of use and constraints around the mapped dimensions. Section 6 concludes with final considerations.

2. Background

Explainability does not exist in a vacuum. Cognitive, behavioral, and sociotechnical factors constrain explainer and recipient heuristics [4]. Early XAI research focused on developer-centric solutions, often tied to mentions of AI principles like *fairness* and *trust*.

Initial research over XAI techniques [1] focused on algorithmic interpretability through local approximations and feature relevance mappings. However, it largely overlooked factors like cognitive limitations, biases, and real-world contextual deployment [5], [3]. Failure to incorporate contextual factors could jeopardize the effectiveness of AI explanations. Qualitative research in XAI has underscored the necessity for safeguards to confirm the robustness of explanations [6], [3]. Despite that, robustness still does not guarantee explanations are useful or beneficial for recipients [7], [8]. The context of use for an explanation is often diverse, influencing user acceptance, understanding, and task performance [9], [5].

Thus, explanations should not be solely perceived as mechanisms to confirm the AI system's abilities or promise added value for users. Even well-articulated, factual explanations might be overshadowed by the system's own accuracy and informativeness if not effectively designed [10]. Furthermore, user acceptance of an explanation does not automatically equate to improved comprehension or functional efficiency. Efforts to bolster transparency via explanations may inadvertently confuse or reinforce undue beliefs or reliance on the AI system, as defined by the concepts of information overload paired to automation and confirmation bias [5], [8].

Thus, safeguards like rigorous testing can help balance transparency to build appropriate trust

and avoid pitfalls. Explainability should be integrated into business organizations in ways that account for cognitive and social biases that shape human judgment (heuristic layers), while also balancing transparency demands for accountability and oversight with confidentiality of user data and proprietary models (transparency trade-offs). As for AI ethics principles, their implementation shall be conceived as a top-down procedure across an organization to quantify potential barriers and risks mitigating their efficacy [2].

In this vein, growing attention has been redirected toward AI policy regulation to balance the rule of law and AI-driven business innovation [11]. Such attention denoted how ensuring compliance over explanation generation is not just a technical, yet a legal and political endeavor [12].

Given the heterogeneity and timing of the EU agenda on digital transformation fostering ICT services such as data, AI, and online platforms, single or partial approaches are now widening the lens from the presumption of a “*right to an explanation*” from the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)⁴ to other regulatory drafts [12], [13], [14]. Yet, no contributions mapped algorithmic explainability regulations with the current EU legal ecosystem.

3. Explainability in the EU Regulations

To identify relevant legal explainability requirements, we conducted a structured search using the *EurLex* database of EU legislation. We focused on binding policies related to data, AI, and digital platforms that shape emerging explainability mandates.

The initial candidate texts were screened to determine inclusion based on containing provisions on algorithmic transparency or explainability. From the final selected regulations, we extracted and qualitatively analyzed articles and recitals with explicit mandates regarding AI system interpretability, transparency or explainability.

Through an iterative coding process among multiple researchers, we categorized these legal provisions into broader explainability themes, dimensions, and involved stakeholders. This al-

⁴For updated legal document versions, we report in footnotes links to EurLex official repository: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>

lowed systematic identification and synthesis of legal explainability requirements across the EU regulatory ecosystem into a summarized mapping. The interested reader can consult the methodology and codebook in the supplemental material [15].

3.1 Data Regulations

3.1.1 General Data Protection Regulation

A discussion on the explainability dimension of algorithmic decision-making (ADM) systems and their legal obligations was triggered already before the GDPR enactment in 2016 [16]. The debate concerned the legitimacy of a “*right to an explanation*” based on the interpretation of recital 71 and Art.22(1) on automated individual decision-making including profiling. Alongside that, Art.13(2)(f), Art.14(2)(g), and Art.15(1)(h) regard the information to be delivered to a data subject⁵ whenever personal data are collected, have not been obtained, or to confirm data processing procedures.

The articles mention the right from the data controller on “*meaningful information about the logic involved, as well as the significance and the envisaged consequences of such processing for the data subject*” in the automated decision. A direction mention in Art.22, where modalities are defined to appeal to this decision and contest it, empowers the data subject to not be exposed “*to a decision based solely on automated processing, including profiling, which produces legal effects*”.

Researchers have explored ambiguities around the requirement to provide information on “*the logic involved*” in ADM system outcomes that profile and affect individuals. The discussion has centered on whether this requirement pertains to data processing rationale or fuller transparency including design choices. As expounded by legal scholars [12], [13], the term “*right*” to an explanation finds a single mention, within a recital, thus holding no binding power. What makes it problematic in its implementation, however, is also the casuistry to which it refers.

The context in which an explanation may be required is based on cases where an ADM system

⁵To note, ‘data subjects’ and ‘data controllers’ are common terms in EU data protection law - the former referring to users whose personal data is processed, the latter to entities like developers responsible for data processing.

operates decisions with legal effects (or the like) on an end-user without *any* human intervention (“*solely*”). This delineation likely invalidates every possible case in which a human operator contributed to the decision about the user, whether AI systems were used as decision-making support services.

Regarding the limitations affecting the efficacy of Art.22, the principle of information proportionality adopted by the EU is relevant. In Art.15(4) there is a mention of how an adversary context (i.e., litigation) jeopardizes this right to obtain information even affecting “*the rights of freedom of others*”. Furthermore, norms on business secrecy⁶ offer a disincentive to disclose information potentially connected to the interests of the controller.

In other words, information obtained by an end-user presumably regards only personal data, excluding ADM systems rationale and the related business design choices conceived. Also, note the lack of legislative precedents for the GDPR as ruled by the Court of Justice of the EU (CJEU) [13], [12]. Constitutional courts can establish if an algorithmic system determined a violation in a specific individual case, yet this will not constitute a general legally binding standard.

3.1.2 Data Act & Data Governance Act

While the GDPR lays harmonized rules regarding foremost the elaboration of personal data, the Data Governance Act (DGA)⁷ enables the provision of common inter-operable data spaces in strategic ICT sectors as designed by the EU Digital Compass. Close to its final draft approval after being proposed in 2020, the DGA was paired in 2022 with a further bill advanced by the EC defined as Data Act (DA)⁸.

The latter outlines data transfer processes and addresses potential information abuses that could

arise from contractual imbalances, potentially obstructing fair access to shared databases. While the DGA and the DA primarily ensure legislative norms for data-sharing, their direct relevance to ADM systems is less pronounced, and they could be considered peripheral to our analysis. Nevertheless, this normative framework provides insights into what constitutes transparency of public data, once again emphasizing the principle of informational proportionality as a cornerstone, as seen in the DGA’s Art.5 on data reuse conditions.

3.2 Artificial Intelligence Regulations

3.2.1 AI Act The major regulatory instance on AI was proposed with the initial AI Act draft (AIA) in April 2021. This subsequently went through extensive debate and revisions, with the final compromise text was officially approved in December 2023⁹ following trilogue negotiations between EU institutions. The approved Act is informed by the principle of proportionality of regulatory intervention for its horizontal approach to risk i.e., being applied broadly across industrial sectors rather than being domain specific. Aside from prohibited ones, this categorization spans three levels of risk - low, medium, and high - with different application limits, transparency requirements, and oversight mechanisms.

AI stakeholders are introduced alongside definitions of risk assessment (Art.9), data quality requirements (Art.10), and extensive technical documentation for authorities (Art. 11, Annex IV); further, for high-risk systems key provisions requiring measures facilitating user interpretability and human oversight (Art. 14).

For interpretability, Art.13 requires instructions explaining system capabilities, limitations and accuracy for high-risk systems, while requiring to attach instructions for use and “*concise, complete, correct and clear*” information to users with respect to “*characteristics, capabilities and limitations of performance*” (Art.13(3)(b)(ii)).

Since the first draft in 2021, scholars inquired what entails the development of “*sufficiently*” transparent systems to allow end-user interpretation of the outputs and enable their appropriate

⁶References to Art. 16 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights; the Directive (EU) 2016/943 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 8 June 2016 on the protection of undisclosed know-how and business information (trade secrets) against their unlawful acquisition, use, and disclosure: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX3A32016L0943>; and the European Parliament Resolution of 20 October 2020 on IP rights for the development of artificial intelligence technologies (2020/2015(ini): https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-9-2020-0277_EN.html

⁷<http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/868/oj>

⁸<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2022:68:FIN>

⁹We analyze the text version later released by the EU Council in February 2024: <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-5662-2024-INIT/en/pdf>, <https://europa.eu/hjMd9Q>

use [12], [13], [14]. To mark, the criterion of “*appropriate*” (Art.13(1),(2)) with regard to the type of transparency hinted an understanding directed for legal sufficiency rather than for a generic end-user. The major issue stood in balancing model complexity, end-user expertise, and business and legal constraints. Indeed, Art.13, does not provide either standards or procedures for evaluating such balances [14], allegedly leaving the transparency assessment at the discretion of the provider of the high-risk system [13].

As for the GDPR, objections to fully interpretable design criteria find appeal in the EU directive establishing trade secret integrity and IP rights. While transparency is desirable to respect EU user rights, it is problematic to unilaterally maximize an AI system transparency when the same users are not controlled over possible misuses [17], [18]. In this regard, end-user liability can be ascertained from the need, expressed in Art.13 and recital(47), for instructions from the provider to the end-user on the intended use. In addition, Art.13(1) disregarded the possibility of using interpretability as a burden of proof by third parties affected by the AI system.

After the final draft delivered by the Permanent Representative Committee in November 2022, the European Parliament voted in mid-June 2023 to approve its negotiating position¹⁰, including notable amendments for guaranteeing algorithmic transparency and individual explainability rights. Among the changes kept in the approved text in February 2024, Art.52¹¹ requires disclosing AI use in human interactions. Even if some amendments of June 2023 were not later retained¹² most significantly Art.68c remained. It

¹⁰https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-9-2023-0236_EN.pdf

¹¹General purpose AI models (GPAI) are defined as systems capable of competently performing a wide range of tasks. Article 52 spans both high-risk as well as GPAI systems interacting with humans or generating synthetic audio/video/text content. For GPAI – classified in Art.52a – requirements mandate transparency documentation disclosing acceptable uses, data/training processes, model capabilities/limitations, and content used in Art.52c. But specifics differ and remain less extensive presently compared to comprehensive rules for high-risk systems [15].

¹²We refer to: (i.) the removed Amend.300 in Art.13 to strengthen transparency – to “*reasonably understand*” the system’s functioning and data used to providers and users, not just interpret outputs – moved now to Art.14(4)(c) and Recital(9b) and (47); (ii.) transparency extensions in Art.29 covered explaining AI logic, capabilities and limitations (Amend.308, 411, 767), with a new recital highlighting transparency and explainability to counter digital asymmetry and “*dark patterns*”(Amend.84).

creates an individual right for those affected by high-risk AI decisions to receive clear explanations about the system’s role, main parameters and inputs with an explicit mention to GDPR. However, exemptions to Art.68c remain possible to protect confidentiality.

3.2.2 AI Liability Directive In September 2022, the proposed directive on the adoption of a system of civil liability for AI (AILD)¹³ was issued to better define those areas of legislative uncertainty during litigation for AI. The proposed AI Liability Directive is directly relevant to real-world explainability requirements, as it aims to address liability gaps that could affect obtaining explanations or recourse.

It makes it easier to bring claims by lowering evidentiary requirements and allowing representative actions. A core provision introduces a rebuttable presumption of causation if three conditions are met: 1) the defendant failed to meet a relevant duty of care such as AIA obligations; 2) their fault likely influenced the AI output or failure to output; and 3) the output or lack of output caused the damage.

This presumption facilitates establishing liability in AI-related cases - only within fault-based scenarios - by connecting the defendant’s actions to the AI system’s role in the damage.

Art. 3 allows potential claimants and courts to request disclosure of relevant documentation and evidence about specific high-risk AI systems from providers or users. This can help claimants access necessary information to determine if an AI system caused damage. Recitals 16-21 explain further this allows claimants to identify liable persons and supports the plausibility of contemplated claims.

The court is empowered to access AI system documentation and design, as stated in Art.4, to validate what is referred to at the time of the inspection as a *presumption of causality* between the damage produced and the system design. Interestingly, Art.4(2)(b),(c) refer to Art.13 of AIA if providers do not meet transparency and oversight requirements for AI system design and development.

¹³<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52022PC0496>

As Recitals 22-30 describe, proving causation can be difficult in AI-enabled damage scenarios given complexity and opacity. Recital 28 specifies how explanations relate to proving causation for opaque AI systems. The duty of care of an AI provider focuses on demonstrating to a mandated supervisory body that the system was compliant only with its instructions for use and documentation. This likely invalidates the possibility for end-users of interpreting system outputs or receiving explanations as a burden of proof under litigation [19].

3.3 Platform Services Regulations

3.3.1 Digital Service Act The DSA¹⁴ defines intermediary due diligence obligations and conditions for liability exemptions related to digital online services, including platforms for online shopping, content-sharing, cloud and messaging services, and marketplaces. The DSA distinguishes between intermediary services, hosting services like online platforms, and "Very Large Online Platforms" (VLOPs).

To enhance transparency in content moderation, the DSA requires all intermediary services to designate a legal representative and describe their methods, including use of algorithmic decision-making systems. Providers must also offer notice mechanisms for allegedly illegal information (Art.9 & 15) and clearly explain terms and conditions for managing third-party content (Art.14).

For advertising, recital 68 enhance transparency for users in platforms service through "*meaningful explanations*" around the ad and such profiling referring to the GDPR. Art.26 requires online platforms to provide transparency into how users are advertised. VLOPs using recommender systems (Art.27) are subject to audits on activities like profiling and targeting recipients, having to explain "*design, the logic, the functioning and the testing of their algorithmic systems*" (Art.40(3)).

Similarly, recital 141 define the Commission to request documentation and explanations about algorithmic systems from all providers. Art.69(2)(d) and (5) grants the Commission authority during inspections to examine algorithms and require platforms to explain system func-

tionality, data practices, and business conducts. Additionally, Art.72(1) enables the Commission to monitor compliance of VLOPs and search engines by ordering access to databases and algorithms, and requiring related explanations via appointed experts (Art.72(2)).

These provisions focus on oversight and compliance rather than mandating interpretability, yet provide authorities tools to request explanations about VLOPs' algorithmic and data systems, enabling investigation of AI systems even if it does not prescribe specific explainability standards.

3.3.2 Digital Markets Act (DMA)¹⁵. While the DSA is focused on regulating online platforms, the DMA aims to regulate the access of companies to digital markets and services. Specifically, it seeks to prevent companies from abusing their position in the market by imposing unfair conditions on other companies in terms of gatekeeper access. In addition, the DMA puts requirements on companies to share data with competitors, which could lead to increased competition. In regards to explainability, Art.21(1),(2) and Art.23 empower the EC to request information and conduct inspections to access data, algorithms, testing information and business practices from gatekeepers. This enables transparency and oversight into the technical processes behind gatekeepers' AI systems as well as their organizational operations.

4. Mapping

To present a comprehensive taxonomy of the different functions corresponding to an explanation, we report specific articles and related recitals in Table 1. The table categorizes regulations by the explainability dimensions and stakeholders they address, providing a useful overview of existing regulatory requirements related to interpretability and explainability of AI systems arising from the policy content analysis.

The table is divided into two main sections: 'Explainability Dimensions' and 'Stakeholders'. The former refers to the different aspects of AI and ADM systems that require explanation, while the latter refers to the entities involved in the AI lifecycle who either provide or receive them.

¹⁴<http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/2065/oj>

¹⁵<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/1925/oj>

	Recital	Explainability Dimension(s)			Stakeholder(s)		
		Data	Process	Business	Auditor	Provider	User
GDPR							
Art.13(2)(f),14(2)(g),15(1)(h)	[60]	[~]	[~]	[x]	-	[G]	[R]
Art.22(3)	[71]	[~]	[x]	-	-	[G]	[R]
AIA							
Art.13(1),(3)	[14a, 47]	[x]	[x]	-	-	[I]	-
Art.14(4)(c)	[48]	[x]	[~]	-	-	[I]	-
Art.52(1)	[48, 70a]	-	[~]	[x]	-	[G]	[R]
Art.68(c)	[84b]	[x]	[x]	[x]	-	[G]	[R]
AILD							
Art.3(1)	[16-21]	-	[~]	[x]	[R]	[G]	-
Art.4(4),(5)	[22-30]	-	[x]	[~]	-	[G]	[R]
DSA							
Art.27(1),(2)	[68]	[~]	-	[x]	-	[G]	[R]
Art.40(3)	[141]	-	[x]	[x]	[R]	[G]	-
Art.69(2)(d),(5)	[146]	[~]	[x]	[x]	[R]	[G]	-
Art.72(1)	[93, 141]	[x]	[x]	[~]	[R]	[G]	-
DMA							
Art.21(1),(2)	[81]	[x]	[x]	[~]	[R]	[G]	-
Art.23(2)(d),(4)	[83]	[~]	[~]	[x]	[R]	[G]	-

Table 1: Mapping of articles referring explicitly to interpretability and explainability dimensions in the EU regulations for AI and ADM systems: [GDPR] = General Data Protection Regulation (2016/679); [AIA] = Artificial Intelligence Act Draft (2021/0106); [AILD] = AI Liability Directive (2022/0303) ; [DSA] = Digital Service Act (2022/2065); [DMA] = Digital Markets Act (2022/1925). For AIA, only high-risk AI systems are considered. Relevant recitals related to articles provision are reported. Explainability Dimension(s) covered in the article provision are signaled with an [x] if explicitly mentioned, while with a [~] to design potential desiderata. Stakeholders are marked with [G] = Giver of an explanation, [R] = Recipient of an explanation, and [I] = Interpreter.

For dimensions, we consult previous mapping work on the operationalization of ethical principles in the AI lifecycle by Georgieva et al. [2]. Their classification is divided into explainability targets such as *technical* for traceability and system description; *process* for decision-making process criteria; *business* for organizational decision-making processes and system design criteria.

We build up on these distinctions to account for a contextual understanding during the due diligence phase or litigation, associated to the stakeholders involved in the AI lifecycle. Explainability requirements are also considered in the sociotechnical context of data and platforms use where an AI system can be implemented.

We intend under *Data* both the temporal side of accessibility and fruition in the ex-ante coordinates (i.e., access to databases) and after processing of the AI system (i.e., data output) but also their topology (i.e., user profiling or reference sampled group). Under *Process* we refer to the architecture and capabilities of an AI system. Under *Business* we refer to business choices that designed the AI system, the acknowledgment to user of interacting with it, and also the social ef-

fects of an AI system of shaping an organization’s business policy and affecting third parties.

As previously illustrated in Section 3, articles and recitals may ambiguously define interpretability or explainability targets. For example, the concept “*logic involved*” in Art.22 of GDPR varies case by case, allegedly including only the processing of personal data to system design and related business choices.

As a precaution, we use the *tilde* symbol to designate legislative ambiguity on *what* (target) can be explained. Additional to the table, we define *how* (type) something can be explained. We draw on the typology advanced by Cabitza et al. [20] for their degree of sufficiency in covering the major casuistry for AI explanations.

Their work differentiates explainability types as *computational* (i.e., how the algorithm produced any output); *mechanistic* (i.e., why so); *justificatory* (i.e., why the output is deemed as right); *causal* (i.e., which factors and how caused the output); *informative* (i.e., the implications of the output); and *cautionary* (i.e., the uncertainty behind an output). In line with these considerations, we view types of explainability desiderata

as neither mutually exclusive nor rigidly defined.

However, we do identify certain interpretative tendencies. Mechanistic and computational types potentially encompass the enhancement of technical interpretability via XAI methodologies to describe an AI system's data output and process. Justificatory and causal explanations are desirable when a business explanation needs to be provided and supported by technical explanations, establishing a heuristic ground-truth of the system being explained. These explanations could also serve as evidence subject to cross-examination under litigation. Informative and cautionary explanations, on the other hand, add layers of semantic granularity, i.e., they advance epistemological knowledge about the system analyzed. Their teleological nature addresses future uncertainty and is more closely related to business explainability, informing users or organizations about remedies to achieve compliance or improve user services.

For stakeholders we advance three macro categories emerging from the analysis of regulations. By *User* we mean service clients, data subjects, or claimants; by *Provider* we refer to both AI providers and general deployers of ADM systems, also in platform services; with *Auditor*, we intend oversight bodies including legal persona delegated to conduct audits.

5. Discussion

Building upon the mapping of explainability dimensions and provisions in Sections 3 and 4, this discussion explores competing tensions around explainability situated across various contexts of use, from oversight procedures to user services and litigation dispute as shown in Figure 1. Balancing transparency for accountability with confidentiality concerns emerges as a central challenge. Regulators seek explainability to audit systems, while providers shield proprietary details. Users impacted by AI decisions desire recourse through understanding, but legal and technical ambiguities persist around useful explainability. We propose a functional view of explanation types [2], [20] based on these scenarios.

To illustrate core explainability issues independent of a specific regulatory context, we present an example of an AI hiring system in

an online platform, e.g., for job advertising and screening, to be deemed as high-risk under the AIA. Through this example, we explore cross-sector tensions between explainability desires and transparency barriers. Rather than focus narrowly on hiring, we aim to highlight key considerations for trustworthy AI broadly. By anchoring analysis in this scenario, we strengthen principles of ethical AI with practical challenges organizations encounter.

5.1 Explainability for Controller Oversight

AI explainability can be leveraged as a risk management tool in oversight procedures. Auditors, related to the EC or national legal bodies, request explainability from AI/ADM service providers or deployers to ensure legislative compliance.

Requests for explanations can occur either as a standard oversight procedure (e.g., for job platforms advertising in the DSA) or as an exceptional case due to litigation (e.g., for an alleged presumption of causality on the harms produced by faults in an AI system over a claimant in the AILD).

Explainability, during an oversight procedure, is addressed transversely in an organization. Even if explanations are generated automatically by an XAI technique, liability spans across an organization's managerial empowered figures (e.g., data protection officers or C-suite) or technical ones (e.g., data scientists and engineers). Legal dispositions generally interpret explainability as granting access to data, algorithms, and business models. Maintained confidentially within supervision bounds, transparency constraints during disclosure should be minimal given the binding power of regulations.

During oversight, auditors are expected to specify the supervision scope, outlining the process, objectives, and involved systems. They can request explanations to providers for specify remedies over preliminary non-compliance e.g., if an AI or ADM system in a provider's platform (DSA - Art.69, Art.72) might results biased in recommending job announcements to certain demographics of applicants. Companies using these high-risk AI systems must provide clear and meaningful explanations of their decision-making processes, including the AI system's role, the

Figure 1: Contexts of use highlighted by discrepancies within different stakeholders involved in the generation and reception of explanations. On an outside layer, transparency constraints are found related to different contexts of use. An additional axis is proposed to locate the explainability area, respectively from AI or ADM systems to the business organization.

main decision parameters, and the related input data (AIA - Art.68(c)).

Despite the principle of proportionality, the sufficiency level to satisfy an audit scope seems to be at the auditor’s discretion, leaving room for interpretation regarding the target and type of explanation.

Transparency Trade-offs – Regulations also allow for exceptions or restrictions to full transparency under certain conditions.

According to Art.68(c)(2) of AIA, the obligation to provide explanations does not apply to the use of AI systems for which exceptions or restrictions are provided under EU or national law, as long as they respect fundamental rights and are deemed as necessary and proportionate.

At the organizational level, exposing additional information might endanger business secrecy as well as third parties. Aside from users maliciously exploiting the system, public exposure of its features might disincentivize market competitiveness of AI-empowered services offered by a provider. This could discourage providers’ business drivers due to enhanced EU regulatory pressure. Yet, regulatory prototyping could reduce compliance costs, informing the debate on standardization practices [11].

Additionally, measures to shield business secrecy and IP are defined in the DMA to protect against unfair digital market competition. In this vein, as an example, Art.3(4) of AILD mentions the Trade Secret Directive (EU) 2016/943 as a baseline for evaluating proportionality and confidentiality of information being disclosed.

Aside from directly affected organizations, increasing transparency may endanger the privacy of third parties if differential measures are not set in place. This might result in a GDPR violation to implement appropriate technical and organizational measures to ensure a level of security appropriate to the risk (Art.32). This type of breach primarily regards interpretability and explainability on target data even before algorithms and business.

Viable XAI Solutions – When implementing explainability for regulatory oversight of the AI hiring system, several XAI approaches can help balance compliance needs with other constraints.

Context-aware, participatory design processes are imperative to reconcile transparency for accountability with confidentiality of user data and business practices.

Inspecting globally interpretable models like *Generalized Additive Models* (GAMs) [1] - despite their limited applicability to high-risk systems if constituted of complex deep neural networks - could provide regulators insights into feature impacts on hiring decisions in a globally interpretable way while protecting raw parameters. Interactive counterfactual scenarios tailored to the hiring context could also demonstrate how changes to applicant profiles alter outcomes, without exposing personal information if properly aggregated - still considering their reliance on assumptions about feature independence and locality that may not fully hold.

However, inherent tensions remain between openness for avoiding direct and indirect discrim-

ination and protecting legitimate trade secrets. Advanced techniques like multi-party computation through federated learning could enable collective auditing without exposing raw data, but incur substantial coordination costs, especially for smaller organizations.

Overall, the precise XAI techniques used in the hiring system must be selected based on legal guidance under EU non-discrimination law and extensive consultation across affected stakeholders. Explanations sufficient for regulatory compliance differ from those useful for applicants or the business itself.

5.2 Explainability for user services

While explainability serves accountability purposes for regulators, additional considerations arise around useful explainability for end user groups affected by AI systems.

In AIA, Art.68(c) grants individuals affected by high-risk AI decisions the right to request clear explanations about the system's role, main parameters, and related input data. In a similar vein, the GDPR and recital 68 in the DSA hint to such recourse mechanism.

Additionally, Art.13 and Art.52 in AIA require high-risk AI systems be designed and developed to ensure sufficient transparency for providers, users, and affected individuals to reasonably comprehend and interpret the system's functioning.

Applied to a hiring context (high-risk scenario for AIA Annex III), this means applicants not selected by an AI screening system could seek understandable explanations about how the system contributed to the decision, what key factors and applicant profile features influenced the outcome, and what personal and training data were utilized.

Together these provisions aim to make opaque AI systems used in impactful contexts like hiring more transparent and explainable to those affected and obliged to deploy them responsibly. However, tensions around useful explainability, accountable oversight, and legitimate secrecy persist.

The degree of sufficiency for the target and type of explanation remains undefined. For instance, it is unclear what constitutes *relevant* input data (AIA - Art.13, Art.68(c)), whether it refers to personal information or general training and fine-tuning data. Similarly, the term *param-*

eters involved (Art.68(c)) could be interpreted as referring to feature relevance, but this is not explicitly stated. The overall design of the high-risk AI system is also to be explained, but the level of granularity required is not specified.

In terms of XAI methods [1], LIME provides intuitive local explanations by constructing linear surrogate models to approximate the behavior of complex machine learning models like deep neural networks. Despite nonlinearity in the full model, LIME allows interpreting individual predictions locally. Alternative techniques like SHAP can explain non-linear models but require disclosure of global model mechanics, which could reveal IP. Interactive counterfactual interfaces enable applicants to tweak inputs and visualize outcomes, empowering them to improve future job applications.

Yet, safeguards like differential privacy and access controls are imperative when exposing counterfactual features, as excessive transparency risks of users unfairly exploiting it [17], [11]. Multi-modal explanations combining saliency maps, partial dependence plots, and natural language could provide complementary views for end-users with different backgrounds. But robustness to perturbation, cognitive load and user fatigue require careful human-centered design [5].

Therefore, considering evaluation metrics and conducting empirical studies to validate explanation quality across user groups is critical [8], [9]. Beyond picking convenient XAI techniques, responsible implementation demands extensive testing to ensure explanations truly empower users without introducing harms [17], [4].

5.3 Explainability for litigation

When alleged harms prompt legal action, explanations face renewed scrutiny in litigation contexts, subject to evidentiary standards.

Under the GDPR and the AIA, an explanation would likely focus on the processing of end-users' personal data, without revealing the decision-making process and design choices made by the AI provider. The choice of XAI methods is left to the provider's discretion, and such provision, likely holds an *exemplificative* value (AIA - Art.14(4)(c)). This discretion does not ensure reference standards or evaluation criteria regarding the suitability or accuracy of the

provided method.

Therefore, beyond the context of oversight, end-users are likely exempted from any legal recourse within their interpretation or explanations since explanation types are upon providers' discretion [12], [13]. This could foster a context of information asymmetry where providers have no real incentive to use interpretable models to safeguard business secrecy, nor are considered liable once generic instructions or explanations are generated.

In a class-action lawsuit alleging discriminatory effect of the AI hiring system, the company would need to reveal the model's inner workings to an auditor – including the features it considers and their assigned weights. Under the proposed AILD, if claimants provide sufficient evidence of system opacity or complexity, they can appeal for a court-ordered audit process. The court could access the AI system's documentation and design to validate claimant's allegations. Failure to meet this interpretability requirement (AIA Art.13) could be used against the company in court. Conversely, the company could argue system compliance with its instructions for use and documentation, shifting liability to the end-user.

In this hiring litigation scenario, automated explanatory systems could enforce presumptive causality disincentivizing providers' XAI use, since it risks becoming a burden of proof against them. Yet interpretable models like GAMs offer explanatory compliance evidence without full model exposure. Counterfactual scenarios tailored to hiring contexts may also showcase non-discrimination through localized tweaking inputs, with proper anonymity protections.

Overall, selective XAI techniques are beneficial if compliance can be demonstrated without requiring full model disclosure. Informative explanations could reflect adopted design criteria, while cautionary ones outline uncertainties around instructions and intended use [20]. Companies shall proactively adopt suitable explainability to verify fairness and mitigate litigation risks, aware of trade-offs between court-mandated transparency and legitimate secrecy around proprietary models.

6. Conclusion

Explainability principles endorsed through regulations must balance transparency for accountability with confidentiality barriers and recourse obstacles. This analysis highlights open challenges transitioning ideals into organizational processes.

Central findings emerge on managing tensions. Theoretically, first by balancing transparency for accountability against confidentiality protections. This translate to an explanation typology spanning technical functions justifying system logic to informative ones guiding business practices. Practically, organizations must proactively adopt lawful, customized transparency balancing compliance risks and constraints. Standardization efforts should acknowledge multi-dimensional tensions between principles and organizational processes. Technologists specifically must assess explanations to empower users without introducing new barriers or potential harms.

Further empirical research can provide nuanced insights on realizing explainability amidst constraints, directing policy and enforcement. Overall, explainability requires context-aware customization balancing demands and protections. But legal compliance alone does not guarantee ethical deployment absent remedies enabling individuals, especially those vulnerable, to challenge algorithmic decisions affecting them.

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REFERENCES

1. A. B. Arrieta, N. D. Rodríguez, J. D. Ser, A. Bennetot, S. Tabik, A. Barbado, S. García, S. Gil-Lopez, D. Molina, R. Benjamins, R. Chatila, and F. Herrera, "Explainable artificial intelligence (XAI): concepts, taxonomies,

- opportunities and challenges toward responsible AI,” *Inf. Fusion*, vol. 58, pp. 82–115, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inffus.2019.12.012>
2. I. Georgieva, C. Lazo, T. Timan, and A. F. van Veenstra, “From AI Ethics principles to data science practice: A reflection and a gap analysis based on recent frameworks and practical experience,” *AI Ethics*, Jan. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43681-021-00127-3>
 3. M. Langer, D. Oster, T. Speith, H. Hermanns, L. Kästner, E. Schmidt, A. Sesing, and K. Baum, “What do we want from Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)? – A stakeholder perspective on XAI and a conceptual model guiding interdisciplinary XAI research,” *Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 296, Jul. 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.artint.2021.103473>
 4. A. Páez, “The pragmatic turn in explainable artificial intelligence (XAI),” *Minds Mach.*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 441–459, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11023-019-09502-w>
 5. A. Bertrand, R. Belloum, J. R. Eagan, and W. Maxwell, “How Cognitive Biases Affect XAI-Assisted Decision-Making: A Systematic Review,” in *Proceedings of the 2022 AAAI/ACM Conference on AI, Ethics, and Society*, ser. AIES '22. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2022, p. 78–91. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3514094.3534164>
 6. D. C. Elton, “Common Pitfalls When Explaining AI and Why Mechanistic Explanation Is a Hard Problem,” in *Proceedings of Sixth International Congress on Information and Communication Technology*, X.-S. Yang, S. Sherratt, N. Dey, and A. Joshi, Eds. Singapore: Springer Singapore, 2022, vol. 235, pp. 401–408, series Title: Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-2377-6_38
 7. T. Miller, “Explanation in Artificial Intelligence: Insights from the Social Sciences,” *Artif. Intell.*, vol. 267, pp. 1–38, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.artint.2018.07.007>
 8. G. Bansal, T. Wu, J. Zhou, R. Fok, B. Nushi, E. Kamar, M. T. Ribeiro, and D. Weld, “Does the whole exceed its parts? the effect of ai explanations on complementary team performance,” in *Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, ser. CHI '21. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3411764.3445717>
 9. R. R. Hoffman, S. T. Mueller, G. Klein, and J. Litman, “Metrics for explainable AI: challenges and prospects,” *CoRR*, vol. abs/1812.04608, 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1812.04608>
 10. A. Papenmeier, D. Kern, G. Englebienne, and C. Seifert, “It’s complicated: The relationship between user trust, model accuracy and explanations in ai,” *ACM Trans. Comput.-Hum. Interact.*, vol. 29, no. 4, mar 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3495013>
 11. M. Fenwick, E. P. M. Vermeulen, and M. Corrales, “Business and Regulatory Responses to Artificial Intelligence: Dynamic Regulation, Innovation Ecosystems and the Strategic Management of Disruptive Technology,” in *Robotics, AI and the Future of Law*, ser. Perspectives in Law, Business and Innovation, M. Corrales, M. Fenwick, and N. Forgó, Eds. Singapore: Springer, 2018, pp. 81–103. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-2874-9_4
 12. P. Hacker and J.-H. Passoth, “Varieties of AI Explanations Under the Law. From the GDPR to the AIA, and Beyond,” in *xxAI - Beyond Explainable AI: International Workshop, Held in Conjunction with ICML 2020, July 18, 2020, Vienna, Austria, Revised and Extended Papers*, ser. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, A. Holzinger, R. Goebel, R. Fong, T. Moon, K.-R. Müller, and W. Samek, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2022, pp. 343–373. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-04083-2_17
 13. M. Ebers, “Regulating Explainable AI in the European Union. An Overview of the Current Legal Framework(s),” Rochester, NY, Aug. 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3901732>
 14. F. Sovrano, S. Sapienza, M. Palmirani, and F. Vitali, “Metrics, Explainability and the European AI Act Proposal,” *J*, vol. 5, pp. 126–138, Feb. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/j5010010>
 15. L. Nannini, J. M. Alonso-Moral, A. Catala, M. Lama, and S. Barro, “Supplemental Material - Operationalizing Explainable AI in the EU Regulatory Ecosystem (1.0),” Zenodo, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10792499>
 16. B. Goodman and S. Flaxman, “European Union Regulations on Algorithmic Decision-Making and a “Right to Explanation,”” *AI Magazine*, vol. 38, no. 3, pp. 50–57, Oct. 2017, number: 3. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1609/aimag.v38i3.2741>
 17. M. Ananny and K. Crawford, “Seeing without knowing: Limitations of the transparency ideal and its application to algorithmic accountability,” *New Media Soc.*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 973–989, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444816676645>

18. A. Bringas Colmenarejo, L. Nannini, A. Rieger, K. M. Scott, X. Zhao, G. K. Patro, G. Kasneci, and K. Kinder-Kurlanda, "Fairness in agreement with european values: An interdisciplinary perspective on ai regulation," in *Proceedings of the 2022 AAAI/ACM Conference on AI, Ethics, and Society*, ser. AIES '22. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2022, p. 107–118. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3514094.3534158>
19. S. Bordt, M. Finck, E. Raidl, and U. von Luxburg, "Post-hoc explanations fail to achieve their purpose in adversarial contexts," in *2022 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, ser. FAccT '22. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2022, p. 891–905. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3531146.3533153>
20. F. Cabitza, A. Campagner, G. Malgieri, C. Natali, D. Schneeberger, K. Stöger, and A. Holzinger, "Quod erat demonstrandum? Towards a typology of the concept of explanation for the design of explainable AI," *Expert Syst. Appl.*, vol. 213, no. Part, p. 118888, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2022.118888>

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